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A Review of Bio Medicine Compounds Derived from Plant Sources and Their Actions.

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ABSTRACT

Medicinal plants based traditional systems of medicines are playing an important role in providing healthcare to large section of population, especially in developing countries. Herbal medicines are the fundamental method adopted in traditional methods to cure various diseases and physiological conditions. They are Siddha, Ayurveda, Unani, Folklore, Ethanomedicine and Naturopathy. Some of the traditional medicines are still used by man for their habitual treatment for various diseases. Phyto-chemicals are non-nutritive plant chemicals that have protective or disease preventive properties. Phytochemicals are used for the prevention and treatment of many health conditions including cancer, heart disease, diabetes, blood pressure, kidney disease, psychiatric illness, skin disease and arthritis and high blood pressure. The most important of these bioactive constituents of plants are steroids, terpenoids, carotenoids, flavanoids, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, tannins and glycosides. Medicinal plant drug discovery continues to provide new and important leads against various pharmacological targets including cancer, HIV/AIDS, Alzheimer's disease. List of Bio Medicines derived from plant sources were collected and searched in the published papers, research articles, text books and grey articles. In those more than 75 % are identified from the published papers and research articles. Remaining 25 % only obtained from text books and grey articles. Totally 123 bio-medicine compounds were identified from various plant sources, these compounds are used in many form of medicines in modern system as chemical entity. It is concluding that most of the bio medicine compounds were isolated or modified only from plant sources. The individual compounds may produce more adverse effects but the natural plant sources are very much less to produce complications when they are given in a appropriate doses.

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INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants based traditional systems of medicines are playing an important role in providing healthcare to large section of population, especially in developing countries. Interest in them and utilization of herbal products produced based on them is increasing in developed countries^[1]. It is a well-known fact that traditional systems of medicines always played an important role in meeting the global healthcare needs. They are continuing to do so at present and shall play major role in future also. The system of medicines which are considered to be Indian in origin or the systems of medicine, which have come to India from outside and got assimilated into Indian cultures, are known as Indian Systems of Medicine. India has the unique distinction of having six recognized systems of medicine in this category. They are Ayurveda, Siddha, Unani and Yoga, Naturopathy and Homoeopathy^[2].

The mankind discovered the idea that certain plants have healing potential and they contain antioxidant and antimicrobial principles. Plants provide the predominant ingredients of medicines in most medical traditions. Medicinal plants play a vital role in the healthcare system all around the world. India has a rich flora that is widely distributed throughout the country. Since ancient times, man has used the plants to treat the common infectious diseases with some natural folklore methods.

Herbal medicines are the fundamental method adopted in traditional methods to cure various diseases and physiological conditions. They are Siddha, Ayurveda, Unani, Folklore, Ethanomedicine and Naturopathy^[3]. Some of the traditional medicines are still used by man for their habitual treatment for various diseases. Among all the five kingdoms, plant kingdom has proven to be the most useful in the treatment of diseases and they provide an important source of all the world's pharmaceuticals. Plants are now occupying the important vital role in allopathic medicine, herbal medicine, homeopathy and aromatherapy. In this modern world, the medicinal plants are the sources of many important drugs^[4]. The traditional system of medicine mainly consist of two types (1) local or folk or tribal stream (2) codified and organized Indian system of medicines such as Siddha, Ayurveda and Unani etc.^[5]. In India, around 20,000, medicinal plants have been recorded but traditional communities are using only 7000 - 7500 plants to cure various diseases^[6].

Phytochemicals

Phyto-chemicals are non-nutritive plant chemicals that have protective or disease preventive properties. They are non-essential nutrients, which mean they are not required by the human body to sustain life. Plant produces these chemicals to protect them but recent research showed that they can also protect human against diseases. The most important of these bioactive constituents of plants are steroids, terpenoids, carotenoids, flavanoids, alkaloids, phenolic compounds, tannins and glycosides. The anti-inflammatory, cytotoxic, antiplatelet, scavenger and antioxidant properties of prenylflavonoids isolated from the *Artocarpus* plants were reported^[7]. Current research is now directed towards finding the specific compounds in these foods that may account for these healthful effects in humans. Phytochemicals are used for the prevention and treatment of many health conditions including cancer, heart disease, diabetes, blood pressure, kidney disease, psychiatric illness, skin disease and arthritis and high blood pressure. There are evidences that certain phytochemicals help to prevent the formation of potential carcinogens (substances that causes cancer), block the action of carcinogens on their target organs or tissue or act on cells to suppress cancer development^[8,9]. Phytochemicals are used for the prevention and treatment of many health conditions including cancer, heart disease, diabetes, blood pressure, kidney disease, psychiatric illness, skin disease and arthritis and high blood pressure. There are evidences that certain phytochemicals help to prevent the formation of potential carcinogens (substances that causes cancer), block the action of carcinogens on their target organs or tissue or act on cells to suppress cancer development^[10].

MATERIALS & METHODS

List of Bio Medicines derived from plant sources were collected and searched in the published papers, research articles, text books and grey articles. In those more than 75 % are identified from the published papers and research articles. Remaining 25 % only obtained from text books and grey articles. Searched with the identified chemical compounds were used in the treatments through biomedicine on various common ailments.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION

Alkaloids

Alkaloids are one of the largest groups of chemical arsenals which are produced by plants. Many of these metabolic by-products are derived from amino acids and include an enormous number of bitter, nitrogenous compounds. More than 10,000 different alkaloids have been discovered in species from over 300 plant families. Alkaloids often contain one or more carbon rings, usually with a nitrogen atom in the ring^[11]. The position of the nitrogen atom in the carbon ring varies with different alkaloids and with different plant families. In some alkaloids, such as mescaline, the nitrogen atom is not within a carbon ring. Actually, it is the position of the nitrogen atom that affects the properties of these alkaloids. Although they undoubtedly existed long before humans, some alkaloids have remarkable structural similarities with neurotransmitters in the central nervous system of humans, including dopamine, serotonin and acetylcholine^[12].

Steroids

A steroid is a type of organic compound that contains a characteristic arrangement of four cycloalkane rings that are joined to each other. Examples of steroids include the dietary lipid cholesterol, bile acids, the sex hormones estradiol and testosterone and the anti-inflammatory drug dexamethasone. The core of steroids is composed of seventeen carbon atoms bonded together that take the form of four fused rings: three cyclohexane rings (designated as rings A, B and C) and one cyclopentane ring (the D ring). The steroids vary by the functional groups attached to this four-ring core and by the oxidation state of the rings. Sterols are special forms of steroids, with a hydroxyl group at position-3 and a skeleton derived from cholestane^[13] given in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Skeleton derived from cholestane.

Terpenoids

Terpenoids (also called isoprenoids) are secondary metabolites occurring in most organisms, particularly in plants. More than 40,000 individual terpenoids are known to exist in nature with new compounds being discovered every year. A large number of terpenoids show cytotoxicity against a variety of tumor cells and cancer cells. The potential role of naturally occurring terpenoids, from diverse origins, in the chemoprevention and treatment of liver tumors are well documented^[14].

Carotenoids

Among the 600 or more carotenoids in foods, beta-carotene, lycopene and lutein are well-known leaders to reduce the damage from free radicals. Foods high in carotenoids may be effective allies against prostate cancer (beta-carotene); cancers of the mouth, pharynx, esophagus, stomach, colon and rectum (lycopene); and may help in decreasing the risk of macular degeneration (lutein). Foods high in carotenoids include red, orange, deep-yellow and some dark-green leafy vegetables, such as tomatoes, carrots, spinach, Brussels, sprouts, sweet potatoes, winter squash and broccoli^[15].

Flavonoids

A flavanoid function in the plant world seems to attract pollinators to flowers or animals that eat the fruits with the intention that they can disperse the seeds. Flavonoids are found only in plants, so to obtain these components we must eat a diet rich in vegetables. Flavonoids have been shown to have a wide range of biological and pharmacological activities in *in vitro* studies. Examples include anti-allergic, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-microbial (antibacterial, antifungal and antiviral), anti-cancer and anti-diarrheal activities. Structure of flavonoids are given in Fig. 2.

Figure 2. The structure of Flavonoid.

Current research in drug discovery from medicinal plants involves a multifaceted approach combining botanical, phytochemical, biological and molecular techniques. Medicinal plant drug discovery continues to provide new and important leads against various pharmacological targets including cancer, HIV/AIDS, Alzheimer's, malaria and pain^[16]. Some of the drugs derived from plants are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Drugs derived from plant sources and their actions.

S.No	Drug/Chemical	Plant source	Action/Clinical use
1	Acetyldigoxin	<i>Digitalis lanata</i>	Cardiotonic
2	Adoniside	<i>Adonis vernalis</i>	Cardiotonic
3	Aescin	<i>Aesculus hippocastanum</i>	Anti-inflammatory
4	Aesculetin	<i>Frazinus rhychophylla</i>	Anti-dysentery
5	Agrimophol	<i>Agrimonia supatoria</i>	Anthelmintic
6	Ajmalicine	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i>	Circulatory disorders
7	Allantoin	Several plants	Vulnerary
8	Allyl isothiocyanate	<i>Brassica nigra</i>	Rubefacient
9	Anabesine	<i>Anabasis sphylla</i>	Skeletal muscle relaxant
10	Andrographolide	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Baccillary dysentery
11	Anisodamine	<i>Anisodus tanguticus</i>	Anticholinergic
12	Anisodine	<i>Anisodus tanguticus</i>	Anticholinergic
13	Arecoline	<i>Areca catechu</i>	Anthelmintic
14	Asiaticoside	<i>Centella asiatica</i>	Vulnerary
15	Atropine	<i>Atropa belladonna</i>	Anticholinergic
16	Benzyl benzoate	Several plants	Scabicide
17	Berberine	<i>Berberis vulgaris</i>	Bacillary dysentery
18	Bergenin	<i>Ardisia japonica</i>	Antitussive
19	Betulinic acid	<i>Betula alba</i>	Anticancerous
20	Borneol	Several plants	Antipyretic, analgesic, anti inflammatory
21	Bromelain	<i>Ananas comosus</i>	Anti-inflammatory, proteolytic
22	Caffeine	<i>Coffeia robusta</i>	CNS stimulant
23	Camphor	<i>Cinnamomum camphora</i>	Rubefacient
24	Camptothecin	<i>Camptotheca acuminata</i>	Anticancerous
25	(+)-Catechin	<i>Potentilla fragarioides</i>	Haemostatic
26	Chymopapain	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Proteolytic, mucolytic
27	Cissampeline	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i>	Skeletal muscle relaxant
28	Cocaine	<i>Erythroxylum coca</i>	Local anaesthetic
29	Codeine	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Analgesic, antitussive
30	Colchicine amide	<i>Colchicum autumnale</i>	Antitumor agent
31	Colchicine	<i>Colchicum autumnale</i>	Antitumor agent, anti-gout
32	Convallatoxin	<i>Convallaria majalis</i>	Cardiotonic
33	Curcumin	<i>Curcuma longa</i>	Choleretic
34	Cynarin	<i>Cynara scolymus</i>	Choleretic
35	Danthron	<i>Cassia species</i>	Laxative
36	Demecolcine	<i>Colchicum autumnale</i>	Antitumor agent
37	Deserpidine	<i>Rauwolfia canescens</i>	Antihypertensive, tranquillizer
38	Deslanoside	<i>Digitalis lanata</i>	Cardiotonic
39	L-Dopa	<i>Mucuna sp</i>	Anti-parkinsonism
40	Digitalin	<i>Digitalis purpurea</i>	Cardiotonic
41	Digitoxin	<i>Digitalis purpurea</i>	Cardiotonic
42	Digoxin	<i>Digitalis purpurea</i>	Cardiotonic
43	Emetine	<i>Cephaelis ipecacuanha</i>	Amoebicide, emetic

44	Ephedrine	<i>Ephedra sinica</i>	Sympathomimetic, antihistamine
45	Etoposide	<i>Podophyllum peltatum</i>	Antitumor agent
46	Galanthamine	<i>Lycoris squamigera</i>	Cholinesterase inhibitor
47	Digitalin	<i>Digitalis purpurea</i>	Cardiotonic
48	Glaucaurubin	<i>Simarouba glauca</i>	Amoebicide
49	Glaucine	<i>Glaucium flavum</i>	Antitussive
50	Glasiovine	<i>Octea glaziovii</i>	Antidepressant
51	Glycyrrhizin	<i>Glycyrrhiza glabra</i>	Sweetener
52	Gossypol	<i>Gossypium hirsutum</i>	Male contraceptive
53	Hemsleyadin	<i>Hemsleya amabilis</i>	Bacillary dysentery
54	Hesperidin	<i>Citrus medica</i>	Capillary fragility
55	Hydrastine	<i>Hydrastis Canadensis</i>	Hemostatic, astringent
56	Hyoscyamine	<i>Hyoscyamus niger</i>	Anticholinergic
57	Irinotecan	<i>Camptotheca acuminata</i>	Anticancer, antitumor agent
58	Kaibic acid	<i>Digenea simplex</i>	Ascaricide
59	Kawain	<i>Piper methysticum</i>	Tranquillizer
60	Kheltin	<i>Ammi visage</i>	Bronchodilator
61	Lanatosides A, B, C	<i>Digitalis lanata</i>	Cardiotonic
62	Lapachol	<i>Tabebuia argentea</i>	Anticancer, antitumor
63	α -Lobeline	<i>Lobelia inflata</i>	Smoking deterrent, respiratory stimulant
64	Menthol	<i>Mentha spicata</i>	Rubefacient
65	Methyl salicylate	<i>Gaultheria procumbens</i>	Rubefacient
66	Monocrotaline	<i>Crotalaria sessiliflora</i>	Antitumor agent (topical)
67	Morphine	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Analgesic
68	Neoandrographolide	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i>	Dysentery
69	Nicotine	<i>Nicotiana tabacum</i>	Insecticide
70	Nordihydro-guaiaretic acid	<i>Larrea divaricata</i>	Antioxidant
71	Noscapine	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Antitussive
72	Ouabain	<i>Strophanthus gratus</i>	Cardiotonic
73	Pachycarpine	<i>Sophora pschycarpa</i>	Oxytocic
74	Palmatine	<i>Coptis japonica</i>	Antipyretic, detoxicant
75	Papain	<i>Carica papaya</i>	Proteolytic, mucolytic
76	Papavarine	<i>Papaver somniferum</i>	Smooth muscle relaxant
77	Phyllodulcin	<i>Hydrangea macrophylla</i>	Sweetner
78	Physostigmine	<i>Physostigma venenosum</i>	Cholinesterase Inhibitor
79	Picrotoxin	<i>Anamirta cocculus</i>	Analeptic
80	Pilocarpine	<i>Pilocarpus jaborandi</i>	Parasympathomimetic
81	Pinitol	Several plants	Expectorant
82	Podophyllotoxin	<i>Podophyllum peltaumt</i>	Antitumor, anticancer agent
83	Protoveratrines A, B	<i>Veratrum album</i>	Antihypertensives
84	Pseudoephedrine	<i>Ephedra sinica</i>	Sympathomimetic
85	Pseudoephedrine, nor-	<i>Ephedra sinica</i>	Sympathomimetic
86	Quinidine	<i>Cinchona ledgeriana</i>	Antiarrhythmic
87	Quinine	<i>Cinchona ledgeriana</i>	Antimalarial, antipyretic
88	Quisqualic acid	<i>Quisqualis indica</i>	Anthelmintic
89	Rescinnamine	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i>	Antihypertensive, tranquillizer
90	Reserpine	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i>	Antihypertensive, tranquillizer
91	Rhomitoxin	<i>Rhododendron molle</i>	Antihypertensive, tranquillizer
92	Rorifone	<i>Rorippa indica</i>	Antitussive
93	Rotenone	<i>Lonchocarpus nicou</i>	Piscicide, Insecticide
94	Rotundine	<i>Stephania sinica</i>	Analgesic, sedative, tranquillizer
95	Rutin	<i>Citrus species</i>	Capillary fragility
96	Salicin	<i>Salix alba</i>	Analgesic
97	Sanguinarine	<i>Sanguinaria Canadensis</i>	Dental plaque inhibitor
98	Santonin	<i>Artemisia maritima</i>	Ascaricide

99	Scillarlin A	<i>Urginea maritime</i>	Cardiotonic
100	Scopolamine	<i>Datura species</i>	Sedative
101	Sennosides A, B	<i>Cassia species</i>	Laxative
102	Silymarin	<i>Silybum marianum</i>	Antihepatotoxic
103	Sparteine	<i>Cytisus scoparius</i>	Oxytotic
104	Stevioside	<i>Stevia rebaudiana</i>	Sweetner
105	Strychnine	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i>	CNS stimulant
106	Taxol	<i>Taxus brevifolia</i>	Antitumor agent
107	Teniposide	<i>Podophyllum peltatum</i>	Antitumor agent
108	α -tetra hydro cannabinol (THC)	<i>Cannabis sativa</i>	Antiemetic, decrease ocular tension
109	Tetra hydro palmatine	<i>Corydalis ambigua</i>	Analgesic, sedative, tranquillizer
110	Tetrandrine	<i>Stephania tetrandra</i>	Antihypertensive
111	Theobromine	<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	Diuretic, vasodilator
112	Theophylline	<i>Theobroma cacao</i>	Diuretic, bronchodilator
113	Thymol	<i>Thymus vulgaris</i>	Antifungal (topical)
114	Topotecan	<i>Camptotheca acuminata</i>	Antitumor, anticancer agent
115	Trichosanthin	<i>Trichosanthes kirilowii</i>	Abortifacient
116	Tubocurarine	<i>Chondodendron tomentosum</i>	Skeletal muscle relaxant
117	Valapotriates	<i>Valeriana officinalis</i>	Sedative
118	Vasicine	<i>Vinca minor</i>	Cerebral stimulant
119	Vinblastine	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Antitumor, Antileukemic agent
120	Vincristine	<i>Catharanthus roseus</i>	Antitumor, Antileukemic agent
121	Yohimbine	<i>Pausinystalia yohimbe</i>	Aphrodisiac
122	Yuanhuacine	<i>Daphne genkwa</i>	Abortifacient
123	Yuanhuadine	<i>Daphne genkwa</i>	Abortifacient

CONCLUSION

The search results submitted in the Table 1 clearly indicates the important of medicinal plants. Totally 123 bio-medicine compounds were identified from various plant sources, these compounds are used in many form of medicines in modern system as chemical entity. Still the isolated phyto-chemical compounds are having their own limitations like adverse and contra indications on regular usage. Most of the bio medicine compounds were isolated or modified only from plant sources. The individual compounds may produce more adverse effects but the natural plant sources are very much less to produce complications when they are given in a appropriate doses. If we use those compounds as a whole plant or decoction (water extract) and Ghee preparations (Fat soluble) should act as a synergistic effect of the medicine to nullify the toxic property and enhance the medicinal curing property. That's why Traditional systems like Siddha and other systems are using the whole or a part of a plant in a particular way to cure the disease.

Recommend for future research:

The herbs used in the Indian Systems of Medicine (ISM) must be preserved for next generations without any changes in their chemical entity. In this context the future research must be designed to save the plant sources from the contamination, pollution and natural calamities.

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Balakrishnan D conceived the concept of the review article and done the collection of data, Selvarajan S done the designing of the study and analysis of data's. Nandhagopal K had done the writing of paper and designing of the manuscript. All authors discussed the methodology, results and conclusions and contributed to the final manuscript.

Conflict of interest:

Conflict of interest declared none.

ABBREVIATIONS

HIV - Human Immunodeficiency Virus.
 AIDS - Acquired Immuno Deficiency Syndrome.
 ISM - Indian Systems of Medicine.

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